

ANALYSIS OF INTERACTION BEHAVIOUR OF ARBITRARY MULTIPLE DEFECTS IN INHOMOGENEOUS MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This study is concerned with the extension of body force method to characterize fracture strength of composite materials containing multiple defects. Through introducing the displacement fundamental solutions and their derivatives, and establishing the suitable displacement and stress boundary conditions at the interfaces of each inclusion and crack, a novel formulation of an improved body force method, which can deal with the mixed-type boundary value problems of inhomogeneous and dissimilar materials with defects, is developed. The preliminary results demonstrate that the proposed method is an effective approach for analyzing the interaction behaviour of arbitrary multiple inclusions and cracks in inhomogeneous and dissimilar materials.

INTRODUCTION

In order to approximately evaluate the strength of composite materials they are sometimes considered as an inhomogeneous solid consisting of homogeneous phases in the engineering sense. However, like all engineering materials, composite materials also contain various kinds of defects, such as inclusions, imperfections, voids and cracks, which may be introduced from the raw materials, during manufacture of the materials, during assembly of the components from these materials, or by degradation in service [1]. Furthermore, the configuration of those defects are often numerous and arbitrary. Consequently the problems of the interaction behaviour of multiple defects have been receiving considerable attention for quantitatively predicting the fracture strength and service lifetime of composite materials containing defects. Only for the problem of a circular inclusion and a crack in an infinite plate, there are a number of papers which have been published, e.g. by Atkinson [2], Erdogan and Gupta [3], Isida and Noguchi [4], Hutchinson [5], Hasebe [6], Wu [7], Tan and Gao [8], Patton and Santare [9], Li and Chudnovsky [10] etc. Those studies are beneficial for understanding the fracture strength of composite materials with defects and also providing some basis for developing other effective numerical methods.

Based on the basic principles of the body force method (BFM) [11], the present study extends this method through introducing displacement fundamental solutions and their derivatives, and

establishing the suitable displacement and stress boundary conditions at the interfaces of each defect to analyze more complicated fracture problems of composite materials containing multiple defects. The preliminary results show that the proposed method proves itself to be excellent in higher precision and faster convergence compared to other methods available when the interaction behaviour of arbitrary multiple defects in inhomogeneous and dissimilar materials are analyzed.

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

Let us consider the general case of an infinite plate with n_i inclusions and n_c cracks with different elastic constants and arbitrary orientations, altogether n defects, subjected to remote complex tensile stresses $\sigma_x^\infty, \sigma_y^\infty$ and shear stress τ_{xy}^∞ , respectively, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. An infinite plate containing multiple inclusions and cracks

Using the BFM to analyze this problem, we first imagine an infinite plate free of defects, but with fictitious inclusions and cracks, the shape and magnitude of which are exactly identical to those of the actual problem. Then we distribute body force densities along the fictitious edges of each defect so as to satisfy the boundary conditions of an actual problem. Consequently the problem of a structure with multiple defects is converted to that of a structure without any defects, but with the corresponding body force densities on the fictitious edges, and solution to the problem is reduced to solving boundary integral equation with unknown body force densities. The stress field at any point inside a solid is then found by linear superposition. Hence the basic concept of the BFM is analogous to the indirect formulation of the boundary element method [12]. However, in order to analyze the problems for the interaction behaviour of multiple defects with different elastic constants as depicted in Fig. 1, the original BFM needs to be developed, and the introduction of displacement fundamental solutions and their derivatives are required so as to satisfy the displacement and stress boundary conditions at the interfaces of each defect.

THE FUNDAMENTAL SOLUTIONS FOR AN INCLUSION PROBLEM

Fig. 2 illustrates the Kelvin problem under the condition of plane strain. The forces F_x, F_y in the figure are represented as point forces applied at (ξ, η) along coordinates (x, y) , respectively. The displacement fundamental solution at any point inside a solid caused by the forces F_x, F_y was given by Kelvin [13] as

$$u_{ik}^{F_k} = \frac{(1-\nu)}{4\pi(1-\nu)E} \left[-(3-4\nu) \ln \delta_{ik} + r_{,i} r_{,k} \right] \quad (1)$$

where π , ν and E are denoted as circle's ratio, Poisson's ratio and Young's modulus of a material, respectively; $r_{,i}$, $r_{,k}$ stand for derivatives of distance r with respect to argument and $r = \sqrt{(x_m - \xi_m)(x_m - \xi_m)}$, in which m is summation symbol; δ_{ik} is a Kronecker delta, which is taken to be 1 if $i = k$, otherwise to be zero; and F_k denotes a point force applied in an infinite plate along the k -axis direction.

Figure 2. Point forces applied at any place in an infinite plate

Differentiating displacements with respect to the argument in (1), and combining with Hooke's law for the stress-strain relationship of a material, the stress fundamental solutions $\sigma_{ij}^{F_x}$, $\sigma_{ij}^{F_y}$ due to point forces F_x , F_y are then determined as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{xx}^{F_x} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{2(1-\nu)x}{x^2+y^2} + \frac{x(x^2-y^2)}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} & \sigma_{xx}^{F_y} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{2\nu y}{x^2+y^2} + \frac{y(x^2-y^2)}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} \\ \sigma_{yy}^{F_x} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{2\nu x}{x^2+y^2} - \frac{x(x^2-y^2)}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} & \sigma_{yy}^{F_y} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{2(1-\nu)y}{x^2+y^2} - \frac{y(x^2-y^2)}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} \\ \sigma_{xy}^{F_x} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{(1-\nu)y}{x^2+y^2} + \frac{2x^2y}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} & \sigma_{xy}^{F_y} &= -\frac{1}{4\pi(1-\nu)} \left\{ \frac{(1-2\nu)x}{x^2+y^2} + \frac{2xy^2}{(x^2+y^2)^2} \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

THE FUNDAMENTAL SOLUTIONS FOR A CRACK PROBLEM

Since a crack can be regarded as the limiting shape of a slender ellipse, we consider the problem of a very slender ellipse in an infinite plate subjected to uniform tension, as depicted in Fig. 3. According to the modified body force densities defined in [12], the displacement and stress tensors at (x, y) induced by tensile body force doublets $2\eta\rho_y d\xi$ and body forces $2\eta\rho_x$ applied at a crack element at $(\xi, 0)$, in which ρ_x, ρ_y are denoted as body force densities, in the figure, are found as

$$u_{ij} = \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} \left(\frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_y=1} + \nu \frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_x=1} \right) \frac{4\sigma_y^\infty}{1-\nu^2} \sqrt{a^2 - \xi^2} d\xi \quad (3a)$$

($i, j = x, y$)

$$\sigma_{ij} = \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_y=1} + \nu \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_x=1} \right) \frac{4\sigma_y^\infty}{1-\nu^2} \sqrt{a^2 - \xi^2} d\xi \quad (3b)$$

($i, j = x, y$)

where $\frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_y=1}, \frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_x=1}$ stand for the derivatives of displacement fundamental solution in (1) with respect to coordinates, and $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_y=1}, \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_x=1}$ the derivatives of stress fundamental solution in (2) with respect to coordinates.

Fig. 3 A crack in an infinite plate subjected to remote tension

Similarly, for the problem of an infinite plate with a crack subjected to remote shear stress τ_{xy}^∞ , as shown in Fig. 4, the displacement and stress tensors induced by shear body force doublets $2\eta\rho_{xy}d\xi$ distributed on the upper and lower surface of the crack plane are determined as

$$u_{ij} = \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} \left(\frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_x=1} + \frac{\partial u_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_y=1} \right) \frac{2\tau_{xy}^\infty}{1+\nu} \sqrt{a^2 - \xi^2} d\xi \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = \int_{\xi_1}^{\xi_2} \left(\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_x}}{\partial \eta} \Big|_{F_x=1} + \frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}^{F_y}}{\partial \xi} \Big|_{F_y=1} \right) \frac{2\tau_{xy}^\infty}{1+\nu} \sqrt{a^2 - \xi^2} d\xi \quad (4b)$$

Fig. 4 A crack in an infinite plate subjected to remote shear stress

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

PROCEDURES OF NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Having a series of expressions for displacement and stress fundamental solutions and their derivatives in the previous section, we can analyze the interaction behaviour of multiple inclusions and cracks with different elastic constants. For the general problem shown in Fig. 1, it is, however, difficult to get a solution in a closed form, numerical analysis is thus required. The numerical procedures are as follows:

First, a varying number of elements along inclusion and crack are discretized in accordance with the relative position, geometrical size, and loading state of each defect. The discretized numbers of elements for each inclusion and crack are denoted as m_i and m_{α} , respectively.

Then, step type body force densities ρ_{sik}, ρ_{nik} and body force doublet densities $\gamma_{sik}, \gamma_{nik}$ are distributed over the elements of inclusions and cracks, respectively. The displacement and stress influence coefficients for an inclusion element under local coordinate system (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) , $u_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\rho_{sik}}, \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\rho_{sik}}$ etc. are computed from the corresponding numerical expressions of eqs. (1) and (2), and $u_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\gamma_{sik}}, \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\gamma_{sik}}$ etc. for a crack element are calculated from the numerical expressions of eqs. (3) and (4).

Next, the boundary conditions are established on the midpoint of each element. For the interface of an inclusion, each point has four conditions: shear displacement, normal displacement, shear stress and normal stress; and for the surface of a crack, there are only two stress conditions on the midpoint of a crack element: shear stress and normal stress. A system of algebraic equations are then set up to find the unknown body force densities that satisfy the prescribed boundary condition of the actual problem.

For the boundary conditions of inclusions, there are

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ki}} (\rho_{sik} u_{sjl}^{\rho_{sk}} + \rho_{nik} u_{sjl}^{\rho_{nk}}) = \sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} u_{sjl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} u_{sjl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + u_{sjl}^{\infty} \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ki}} (\rho_{sik} u_{njl}^{\rho_{sk}} + \rho_{nik} u_{njl}^{\rho_{nk}}) = \sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} u_{njl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} u_{njl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + u_{njl}^{\infty}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ki}} (\rho_{sik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\rho_{sk}} + \rho_{nik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\rho_{nk}}) = \sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + \sigma_{sjl}^{\infty}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n_i} \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ki}} (\rho_{sik} \sigma_{njl}^{\rho_{sk}} + \rho_{nik} \sigma_{njl}^{\rho_{nk}}) = \sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} \sigma_{njl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} \sigma_{njl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + \sigma_{njl}^{\infty}$$

$$j = 1, 2, \dots, n_j; \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, m_{li} \quad j \leq n_i$$

$$l = 1, 2, \dots, m_{ci} \quad j > n_i$$

where $\sigma_{sjl}^{\rho_{sk}} = -(\sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\rho_{sk}} - \sigma_{\bar{y}\bar{y}jl}^{\rho_{sk}}) \sin \beta_{kl} \cos \beta_{kl} + \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{y}jl}^{\rho_{sk}} (\cos^2 \beta_{kl} - \sin^2 \beta_{kl})$

$$\sigma_{njl}^{\rho_{sk}} = \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\rho_{sk}} \sin^2 \beta_{kl} - 2 \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{y}jl}^{\rho_{sk}} \cos \beta_{kl} \sin \beta_{kl} + \sigma_{\bar{y}\bar{y}jl}^{\rho_{sk}} \cos^2 \beta_{kl}$$

$$\sigma_{sjl}^{\gamma_{sk}} = -(\sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}} - \sigma_{\bar{y}\bar{y}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}}) \sin \beta_{kl} \cos \beta_{kl} + \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{y}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}} (\cos^2 \beta_{kl} - \sin^2 \beta_{kl})$$

$$\sigma_{njl}^{\gamma_{sk}} = \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{x}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}} \sin^2 \beta_{kl} - 2 \sigma_{\bar{x}\bar{y}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}} \cos \beta_{kl} \sin \beta_{kl} + \sigma_{\bar{y}\bar{y}jl}^{\gamma_{sk}} \cos^2 \beta_{kl}$$

$$\beta_{kl} = \theta_{ik} - \theta_{jl}$$

and θ_{ik} etc. are meant an inclined angle of the kth element of the ith defects established on local coordinate system (\bar{x}_k, \bar{y}_k) with x-axis of global coordinate system (x, y) ; $u_{sjl}^{\infty}, \sigma_{sjl}^{\infty}$ etc. are referred to the values of displacement and stress at the interface of an inclusion to be considered caused by remote stresses, respectively.

For cracks, the boundary conditions are listed as

$$\sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} \sigma_{sjl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + \sigma_{sjl}^{\infty} = 0 \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{i=n_i+1}^n \sum_{k=1}^{m_{ci}} (\gamma_{sik} \sigma_{njl}^{\gamma_{sk}} + \gamma_{nik} \sigma_{njl}^{\gamma_{nk}}) + \sigma_{njl}^{\infty} = 0$$

$$j = n_i + 1, \dots, n; \quad l = 1, 2, \dots, m_{ci}$$

After solving algebraic equation systems of eqs. (5) and (6), a group of body force densities $\gamma_{sik}, \gamma_{nik}$ are obtained, and stress intensity factors and stress concentration factors are thus determined according to the relevant formula described in more detail in another paper [12].

THE ANALYSIS OF TWO CASE EXAMPLES

An Annulus With Different Elastic Constants Inside A Circular Hole

Fig. 5 shows a simple example of boundary value problem for an inhomogeneous solid. The region of interest is composed of an annulus $r_1 \leq r \leq r_2$ with elastic constants E_i, ν_i inside a circular hole of radius $r = r_2$ in a large plate with elastic constants E_m, ν_m . The inside wall of the annulus is subjected to a normal pressure p, and the plate is unstressed at infinity. The analytical solution to this problem, satisfying continuity of radial displacement and stress at

interface $r = r_2$ were given in a treatise book [14]. If we let $E_i / E_m = 2.0$, $\nu_i = \nu_m = 0.25$, $r_1 / r_2 = 0.5$ and $p / E_i = 10^{-3}$, the results by the present method and analytical method are shown in Table 1.

Figure 5. An annulus with different elastic constants inside a circular hole

Table 1 Computed values for radial and tangential stresses with different numbers of elements for an annulus inside a hole in a large plate

Relative Distance (r / r_1)	Stress	24	36	48	Extrapolated Values	Analytical Solution [14]	Relative Error (%)
1.0	σ_n / p	-1.000	-1.000	-1.000	-1.000	-1.000	0.00
	σ_θ / p	1.250	1.240	1.233	1.212	1.222	0.82
1.5	σ_n / p	-0.398	-0.394	-0.392	-0.386	-0.382	0.14
	σ_θ / p	0.649	0.635	0.628	0.607	0.605	0.30
2.0	σ_n / p	-0.171	-0.169	-0.168	-0.165	-0.167	0.30
	σ_θ / p	0.421	0.409	0.404	0.389	0.388	0.26
	σ_{rm} / p	-0.171	-0.169	-0.168	-0.165	-0.167	0.30
	$\sigma_{\theta m} / p$	0.170	0.169	0.168	0.165	0.167	0.30
2.5	σ_{rm} / p	-0.079	-0.078	-0.077	-0.074	-0.074	0.00
	$\sigma_{\theta m} / p$	0.079	0.078	0.077	0.074	0.074	0.00

Table 1 shows that the computed values by different numbers of elements display excellent linear relationship and show a very fast convergence. Even though the computed value is chosen for only 24 elements, the maximum error at values by the present method and analytical solution is less than 2%. This means that the present method can also reach higher computational precision with a relatively coarse discretization.

The Interaction Behaviour Of Two Circular Inclusions

To further verify that the present method is also valid for more complicated problems, we consider the interaction behaviour of two circular inclusions of radius r in an infinite plate subjected to remote uniform stress, as shown in Fig. 6. Suppose that the Poisson's ratios of both materials, $\nu_i = \nu_m = 0.30$, the relative distance, $r / d = 0.465$, and the discretized numbers of elements for each inclusion are 24 and 36, respectively. The extrapolated values obtained by both discretized numbers of elements are presented in Table 2.

Figure 6 The interaction behaviour of two circular inclusions

Table 2 The interaction behaviour of two circular inclusions in an infinite plate

Young's modulus Ratio (E_i / E_m)	Present Method (Inclusion) (σ_{max} / p)	Literature [15] (Inclusion) (σ_{max} / p)	Relative Error (%)	Present Method (Matrix) (σ_{max} / p)	Literature [15] (Matrix) (σ_{max} / p)	Relative Error (%)
0.5	0.752	0.758	0.85	1.505	1.510	0.34
2.0	1.192	1.200	0.67	1.202	1.207	0.41

In comparison with Shioya's method [15], the extrapolated value has less than 1.0 % of error. It is obvious that the present method is also effective for complicated problems if the interaction behaviour of composite materials with defects are analyzed.

As a result, the improved body force method proposed in this study can be used as an effective tool for evaluating the fracture strength of composite materials containing multiple defects. Detailed results for more general problems for the interaction behaviour of multiple inclusions and cracks with arbitrary orientations will be reported in an another separate paper.

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